

THE COMMUNICATIVE FUNCTIONS OF INTONATION

Khakimova Dilshoda Oybek qizi

dilshodaa.khakimova@mail.ru

Faculty of English philology and teaching, Uzbekistan State World Languages
University, Tashkent, Uzbekistan

ANNOTATION: This article sheds light on intonation in English, communicative functions are also discussed with the viewpoints of scientists.

KEY WORDS: melodic pattern, stress, rhythm, speech, tone.

Intonation is the melodic pattern of speech in phonetics. It conveys differences in expressive meaning (such as surprise, anger, or pleasure), and it can also serve a grammatical function. Intonation is primarily a matter of variation in pitch. In languages like English, it is often accompanied by stress and rhythm to create meaning.

There is no language in the world that is not always spoken in monotone (that is, in the same musical note). Rarely do we speak with a fixed tone. In normal speech, the pitch of our voice is constantly changing; now it goes up, now it goes down, and sometimes it stays at the same level or steady. The different tones of the voice combine to form speech variations or tones that make up the intonation of the language. Thus, the intonation of a language refers to the change in tone or the tones one uses in one's speech. When we talk to each other, our voices "raise" or "lower" in relation to a part of speech. This rise or fall of pitch is called intonation. Falling intonation is indicated by a slanted arrow from left to right, and rising intonation by an arrow that rises from left to right. The arrow is placed only before the last stressed syllable (nucleus). Intonation plays an important role in communication. Intonation is mainly used to express the attitude of the speaker to the listener or to the topic he is talking about. In linguistics, intonation is a change in speech pitch that is not used to distinguish words; Instead, it focuses on showing the speaker's attitudes and feelings, distinguishing between statements and questions and between different

types of questions, drawing attention to important elements of the spoken message, and also making the speech used for functions such as regulatory assistance. conversational interaction. Basic intonation pattern in English: falling tone, rising tone, falling tone and rising tone. Rising intonation means that the pitch rises over time [$\nearrow$]; Falling Intonation means that the pitch decreases over time [$\searrow$]; Fall-rise Intonation falls and then rises [$\searrow\nearrow$]; and Rise-pall Intonation rises and then falls [$\nearrow\searrow$]. Stress and intonation are related phenomena; they work together to give a "prominence" or "highlight" effect. Stressed syllables can be pronounced with a high or low pitch or with a change in pitch. A stressed syllable spoken at a single pitch is described as having static pitch, while a stressed syllable in which pitch changes occur is described as having kinetic pitch. The syllable that begins the kinetic tone is called the nucleus, and is said to have the main, nucleus, or tonic stress. A syllable that is pronounced with a high or low pitch is said to have a static pitch, and a syllable that has a pitch change is said to have a kinetic pitch (moving pitch).

Intonation is an important aspect of spoken English that can convey a wide range of meanings and emotions. It refers to the rise and fall of pitch, stress, and rhythm in speech, and it can greatly affect how the message is received by the listener. In this essay, we will look at the communicative functions of intonation in English and how it can be used to convey different kinds of information. One of the main functions of intonation is to indicate the end of a sentence or phrase. In English, pitch usually rises at the end of a question and falls at the end of a sentence. This helps the listener to understand the difference between a statement and a question and to understand the speaker's intended meaning. For example, consider the following two sentences:

1. *You go to the store.*
2. *Do you go shopping?*

The first sentence is a statement, and the tone falls at the end. The second sentence is a question and the pitch rises at the end. This simple change in intonation can completely change the meaning of a sentence. Another important function of

intonation is to convey stress or emphasis. By emphasizing certain words or syllables, speakers can highlight important information or convey an emotional state. For example, consider the following sentence:

I didn't say you were stupid.

A word can have different meanings depending on the accent. If the word "you" is stressed, it may mean that someone else has called the listener an idiot. If the word "stupid" is stressed, it may mean that the speaker did not use that word, but still meant it. If the word "no" is stressed, it may mean that someone else is calling the listener an idiot. Intonation can also be used to convey different attitudes or emotions, such as sarcasm, anger, or excitement. Depending on the intonation of the sentence, it can convey different emotions. If the tone falls at the end of the sentence, it can mean sarcasm or annoyance. If the tone rises at the end, it can indicate excitement or anticipation.

Finally, intonation can be used to show uncertainty or hesitation. By using rising or falling pitches in a certain way, speakers can convey that they are unsure of something or need clarification.

In conclusion, intonation is a powerful tool for conveying meaning and emotion in spoken English. Speakers use rising and falling pitch, stress, and rhythm in different ways to indicate the end of a sentence or phrase, to convey emphasis or stress, to indicate different attitudes or emotions, to express different meanings, to convey information of a kind, indicate ambiguity or ambiguity. Understanding the communicative functions of intonation is essential for effective English communication.

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